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ABSTRACT

The phase-dependent plasmonic response of a metamaterial platform composed of VO₂ nanocrystals (NCs) embedded in an SiO₂ matrix was investigated using ultrafast time-resolved spectroscopic ellipsometry. Localized surface plasmon resonances (LSPR) emerged upon excitation with 35 fs laser pulses at $\lambda = 500$ nm, which triggered the insulator-to-metal transition in the VO₂ NCs. The study reveals the ultrafast dynamics mapped at the LSPR underlying the photoinduced optical tunability of the system, highlighting the potential of VO₂ NCs for reconfigurable photonic applications such as tunable linear switching.

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The development of metamaterials has revolutionized light control, allowing precise manipulation of amplitude, phase, and polarization. By engineering the arrangement and geometry of meta-atoms, researchers have demonstrated exotic phenomena such as negative refraction and perfect absorption,^{1,2} enabling ultrathin flat lenses,³ beam converters,³ and optical deflectors.⁴ However, early metamaterials were passive, with fixed optical properties at fabrication, limiting their adaptability.

The integration of active materials, whose properties can be dynamically tuned by external stimuli, has enabled the realization of reconfigurable photonic systems. Among various active materials, vanadium dioxide (VO₂) is of particular interest due to its near-room-temperature insulator-to-metal transition (IMT), which leads to significant changes in its optical and electrical properties. Nevertheless, VO₂-based devices face challenges such as high optical losses across the visible to near-infrared spectrum.⁵ To address this, nanostructuring strategies have been employed to reduce losses and enhance tunability, although typically over narrow spectral bands.^{6,7}

While the thermally driven IMT in VO₂ films and nanostructures has been studied extensively,^{5,8,9} including its application in

tunable photonic platforms,^{10–12} the ultrafast photoinduced IMT in VO₂ systems remains comparatively less explored. The ultrafast photoinduced IMT process involves complex interactions between electrons, and phonons, making femtosecond-scale investigations crucial for advancing high-speed photonic devices.^{13–18} At the nanoscale, the IMT proceeds via spatially inhomogeneous nucleation of metallic domains, leading to phase coexistence as revealed through several techniques such as scanning near-field optical microscopy (s-SNOM)^{19–21} and electron microscopy,²² and gives rise to fluence-dependent multilevel optical responses.^{6,23} Although multilevel optical states in VO₂ nanostructured platforms have been demonstrated in several works, the overwhelming majority of these rely on the thermally driven IMT,^{21–23} which is inherently limited to millisecond-to-microsecond switching speeds set by heat diffusion. This fundamentally precludes operation at the speeds required for optical signal processing or neuromorphic photonics. The photoinduced IMT, in contrast, proceeds on femtosecond-to-picosecond timescales, yet demonstrations of multilevel optical modulation driven by the photoinduced IMT in nanostructured VO₂ platforms remain scarce. Recent ultrafast studies on VO₂ nanostructures have explored partial IMT

and fluence-dependent graded responses, but these works typically focus on a small number of probe wavelengths and do not monitor the ultrafast dynamics through a spectrally localized optical mode.^{6,23} As a result, they do not provide a broadband, mode-specific picture of the photoinduced IMT.

In this study, we investigate the ultrafast optical response of a metamaterial composed of VO₂ nanospheres embedded in an SiO₂ matrix undergoing a photoinduced insulator-to-metal transition (IMT). Using ultrafast pump-probe spectroscopic ellipsometry, we track the photoinduced IMT through a spectrally localized surface plasmon mode (LSPR), monitoring its dynamics simultaneously in time and across the visible to near-infrared spectrum. Unlike prior VO₂ studies that focus on one or a few probe wavelengths,^{6,11,23} our approach provides a comprehensive spectral-temporal map of the ultrafast IMT, resolving the real-time evolution of the LSPR mode and enabling fluence-controlled, graded modulation of optical absorption driven by the photoinduced IMT, with at least 10⁷ cycles of demonstrated reversibility. Unlike VO₂ thin films, where optical modulation is spectrally broad and governed by the bulk dielectric function, the spherical nanocrystal geometry confines the dominant optical response to a well-defined localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) near 1000 nm, enabling spectrally selective ultrafast modulation at a targeted wavelength. This spectral confinement is illustrated in Fig. S1, where we compare the imaginary part of the VO₂ bulk dielectric function, which governs the broadband optical response of thin films across the entire visible and near-infrared range, with the pseudo-dielectric function of our nanocrystal-based metamaterial, whose response is concentrated around the LSPR. Notably, the pseudo-dielectric function of the nanocrystal metamaterial exhibits significantly reduced losses compared to bulk VO₂ across the visible and near-infrared range.

Our work is therefore among the very few to demonstrate tunable optical modulation in a resonant VO₂ nanostructured platform driven by the photoinduced IMT, bridging the gap between the extensive static and thermal literature and the practical requirements of ultrafast photonic and neuromorphic devices. These results pave the way for high-speed, reconfigurable photonic devices and offer a unique window into the interplay between structural, electronic, and optical phenomena in nanostructured correlated materials.

The transient complex pseudo-dielectric function $\langle \epsilon \rangle = \langle \epsilon_1 \rangle + i\langle \epsilon_2 \rangle$ was measured using time-resolved pump-probe spectroscopic ellipsometry. The setup, shown in Fig. 1(a), is based on a broadband femtosecond ellipsometer in the following configuration: polarizer-sample-compensator-analyzer.

The experiment was driven by a 35 femtosecond Coherent Astrella laser system operating at 800 nm. The probe supercontinuum (1–3.1 eV) was generated by focusing a 1400 nm pulse, obtained from an optical parametric amplifier (TOPAS), onto a CaF₂ window, this beam was incident at 65° on the sample. The other pulse was converted into a 500 nm *p*-polarized pump pulse using an optical parametric amplifier (TOPAS-PRIME), incident at 60° on the sample. The pump beam was modulated using a mechanical chopper running at 250 Hz, and the probe at 500 Hz, enabling a four-frame detection scheme analogous to a multichannel lock-in amplifier. This repetition rate of the pump ensured full relaxation between pulses. The pump spot size was made larger than the probe to achieve uniform excitation over the studied area. A variable delay line controlled the timing between pump and probe pulses. Transient reflectance-difference

FIG. 1. (a) The pump-probe time-resolved spectroscopic ellipsometer setup includes second harmonic generation (SHG) for the pump beam, supercontinuum white-light generation (SCG) for the probe beam, a delay line (DL), lenses (L), a polarizer (P), a pseudo-rotating compensator (CR), and an analyzer (A). The pump beam operates at a repetition rate of 250 Hz. (b) A cross-sectional schematic illustrates VO₂ nanocrystals (NCs) embedded in an SiO₂ matrix. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images confirm the spherical morphology of the VO₂ NCs within the layer. (c) The absorption efficiency (Q_{abs}) of a spherical VO₂ nanocrystal with a radius of 35 nm embedded in SiO₂ was calculated for both its insulating and metallic phases. The shaded regions indicate the contributions of dipolar electric (a_1), dipolar magnetic (a_2), and quadrupolar magnetic (b_2) resonances to Q_{abs} .

spectra were acquired with a prism spectrometer and a CCD camera at 1 kHz. Calibration included dark measurements (one without the pump, one without the probe, and one without both) and data analysis followed the Mueller Matrix formalism, chirp correction, and weighting against a steady-state ellipsometric spectrum measured with a Park Systems EP4 ellipsometer. Further experimental details are available in Ref. 24.

The pseudo-dielectric function $\langle \epsilon \rangle$ represents a dielectric function obtained directly from the measured ellipsometric parameters (Ψ , Δ) and is calculated from an optical model that assumes our metamaterial as a homogeneous semi-infinite flat substrate.

The VO₂ nanocrystal (NC) metamaterial consists of a dense layer of isolated, nearly spherical VO₂ NCs buried in an SiO₂ matrix

at approximately 100 nm below the surface. The metamaterial was fabricated using ion implantation as described in detail elsewhere.^{7,25,26} Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analysis confirms the successful formation and uniform distribution of the VO₂ NCs beneath the surface. Below, a layer containing vanadium inclusions and impurities is present. As shown in Fig. 1(b), the nanocrystals exhibit consistent spacing, with interparticle distances comparable to their diameters.

From the TEM images, the radius of the NCs is estimated to be approximately 35 nm. Owing to their nearly spherical geometry and subwavelength dimensions in the visible and near-infrared spectral range, their optical response can be accurately described using Mie theory assuming non-interacting particles. This theoretical framework provides an exact solution to Maxwell's equations for spherical particles and enables the calculation of their scattering and absorption properties. Specifically, Mie theory²⁷ expresses the response in terms of Mie coefficients a_n and b_n , which quantify the contributions from electric and magnetic resonant modes, respectively. The index n denotes the multipolar order, where $n=1$ corresponds to dipolar modes, $n=2$ to quadrupolar modes, and higher values to higher-order multipoles.

The optical response of a single VO₂ NC embedded in SiO₂ (with refractive index $n_{\text{med}} \approx 1.45$) was calculated by computing its absorption efficiency Q_{abs} using Mie theory. Figure 1(c) shows the resulting spectra for both the insulating and metallic VO₂ phases. Below 750 nm, the absorption efficiency remains largely unchanged between the two phases, dominated by electric and magnetic dipolar resonances. However, in the metallic state, an increased free carrier density gives rise to an electric dipolar localized surface plasmon resonance (LSPR) at around 1000 nm. This phase-dependent plasmonic behavior enables dynamic switching of the LSPR, making these metamaterials promising candidates for active photonic applications.

While minor spectral shifts arising from interparticle electromagnetic interactions and satellite nanocrystals cannot be fully excluded,⁷ the dominant contribution to the optical response, and, in particular, to the transient response, arises from the electric dipolar resonance of the VO₂ NCs, as evidenced by the close correspondence between the measured transient spectral features and the calculated a_1 mode position shown in Fig. 1(c). Interparticle interactions and satellite NCs may induce secondary spectral modulations, but their effect is relatively small compared to the primary a_1 resonance.

Importantly, the imaginary part of the pseudo-dielectric function $\langle \epsilon_2 \rangle$ measured with spectroscopic ellipsometry is directly correlated with the absorption of the material, which in our metamaterial arises exclusively from the VO₂ nanocrystals as the SiO₂ matrix is non-absorbing. Since the absorption of the NCs corresponds to the calculated absorption efficiency Q_{abs} calculated in Fig. 1(c), a direct correlation can be established between $\langle \epsilon_2 \rangle$ and Q_{abs} .

To study the photoinduced phase transition in the VO₂ nanocrystal (NC) metamaterial, we employed time-resolved pump-probe ellipsometry. The pump wavelength was set at 500 nm, exciting both electric and magnetic dipolar resonances in the NCs, as shown in Fig. 1(c). Different pump fluences were used to study the fluence dependence of the photoinduced IMT. Fluences ranging between 1.2 and 6.1 mJ/cm² were applied.

The pseudo-dielectric function of the metamaterial was probed across the 400–1200 nm range, allowing us to monitor the

development of the a_1 mode during the IMT, particularly around 1000 nm, with time delays extending up to 3.5 ns after excitation.

Figure 2 presents the spectral evolution of imaginary part of the pseudo-dielectric function $\langle \epsilon_2 \rangle$ as a function of the time delays ranging from -0.1 to 3500 ps (3.5 ns) following excitation with a pump pulse at 500 nm and a fluence of 6.1 mJ/cm². These plots correspond to the maximum fluence used, which induces the most significant changes in the optical response of the metamaterial. The plots for the other applied fluences are shown in Figs. S2–S4. Additionally, the figure includes reference measurements of $\langle \epsilon_2 \rangle$ of the same sample at temperatures of 30 (insulating state) and 96 °C (metallic state). This allows direct comparison between thermally- and photoinduced IMT in the NCs. The temperature dependent behavior of this metamaterial has already been deeply studied in Ref. 7. The discrepancy observed at 1200 nm between the reference and pump-probe data are attributed to the use of different optical setups and sample holders for each

FIG. 2. Transient imaginary parts of the pseudo-dielectric function $\langle \epsilon_2 \rangle$ in the time delay intervals of (a) $[-0.1, 1]$ ps, (b) $[1, 100]$ ps, and (c) $[200, 3500]$ ps. The pump characteristics are $\lambda_{\text{pump}} = 500$ nm and fluence $F_{\text{pump}} = 6.1$ mJ/cm². As a reference, these plots also show the $\langle \epsilon_2 \rangle$ at 30 and 96 °C.

measurement, which may introduce systematic spectral offsets in regions of rapidly varying transmission.

It is evident that the photoinduced IMT exhibits a spectral signature that closely mimics the thermally induced IMT, characterized by the emergence of a peak in the near-infrared region associated with the excitation of an electric dipolar LSPR in the VO₂ nanocrystals closely aligning with the Q_{abs} spectra shown in Fig. 1(c).

To study the dynamics of photoinduced IMT as a function of the fluence of the pump, Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) show $\Delta\langle\epsilon_2\rangle$, i.e., the changes in the imaginary part of the pseudo-dielectric function as a function of the time delay. These values are monitored at $\lambda = 1000$ nm, where the a_1 LSPR is excited in the metallic state. To better illustrate the scale of the excitation dynamics of the IMT in the VO₂ NCs, two delay intervals are plotted: (a) -1 to 5 ps and (b) -5 to 50 ps.

For $F_{\text{pump}} > 1.2$ mJ/cm², the curves show similar dynamics during IMT excitation. This consists of a fast sharp increase in $\Delta\langle\epsilon_2\rangle$, followed by a long-lived slow rise of the signal. This behavior has been phenomenologically fitted in the first 50 ps to

$$\Delta\langle\epsilon_2\rangle(t) = C + \Theta(t) - A_0 e^{-t/\tau_{ps}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\Theta(t) = \frac{A_1}{1 + e^{-\alpha(t-\beta)}}$ is a logistic sigmoidal function. A_0 , A_1 , C , α , and β are the fitting parameters. The values of the fitting parameters are provided in Table S1. The sigmoidal function describes a fast non-

FIG. 3. Time-resolved transient changes in the imaginary part of the pseudo-dielectric function (ϵ_2) at 1000 nm in different time delay ranges after the pump: (a) -1 to 5 ps and (b) -5 to 50 ps. Each curve represents the dynamics for different F_{pump} . The black solid line is the fitting to Eq. (1). (c) Value of $\Delta\langle\epsilon_2\rangle$ measured at 1000 nm and delay time of 0.5, 1, and 50 ps.

thermal process, which is ascribed to the photoinduced nucleation of the metallic phase.²⁸ This process has a characteristic time τ_{fs} of several hundreds of femtoseconds. The speed at which the photoinduced nucleation (ν_n) occurs can be related to the steepness of the sigmoidal function. This parameter is evaluated as the value of the derivative at the inflection point ($\nu_n = A_1\alpha/4$), and it increases with F_{pump} . The exponential term in the equation describes a slower process with a rise time τ_{ps} in the order of a few picoseconds, associated with the thermally driven growth and coalescence of metallic domains in the material.¹² This model has been successfully used to describe the transient optical response of VO₂ thin films.²⁹ The fact that the characteristic timescales and phenomenological dynamics are preserved in the nanocrystal geometry is itself a non-trivial finding: it demonstrates that the fundamental ultrafast IMT mechanism (i.e., sub-ps non-thermal nucleation followed by ps-scale thermally driven growth) survives geometric confinement and the mechanical boundary conditions imposed by the SiO₂ matrix. In contrast, for $F_{\text{pump}} = 1.2$ mJ/cm², the $\Delta\langle\epsilon_2\rangle$ profile exhibits rapid switching that can be modeled using only the logistic sigmoidal function, followed by an almost constant value.

To investigate how changes in the optical response scale with F_{pump} , Fig. 3(c) presents the fluence-dependent variation $\Delta\langle\epsilon_2\rangle$ at 1000 nm, measured 0.5, 1, and 50 ps after excitation. The results show a clear linear relationship between $\Delta\langle\epsilon_2\rangle$ and F_{pump} , suggesting that an increasing fraction of VO₂ nanocrystals undergoes the insulator-to-metal transition as the pump fluence rises. This trend is consistent with previous observations in VO₂ thin films,²⁹ suggesting that the fundamental dynamics of the photoinduced transition remain similar despite structural differences between thin films and nanostructured metamaterials. Crucially, this linearity provides a direct and precise means to control the optical absorption of the system by tuning the pump fluence, enabling access to a continuous set of intermediate absorption states between the fully insulating and fully metallic limits. This fluence-controlled, graded modulation is particularly advantageous for reconfigurable photonics, where deterministic access to multiple distinct optical states is required. Importantly, the IMT in VO₂ is fully reversible upon relaxation to the insulating phase, and the nanocrystal platform has been shown to sustain this switching cycle for at least 10^7 consecutive excitation events without measurable degradation, a figure that underscores its robustness for practical device applications. The present measurements span the range 1.2–6.1 mJ/cm², over which the response remains strictly linear with no evidence of saturation; accessing the saturation regime would require fluences beyond what our current experimental geometry allows and is therefore identified as an important direction for future work.

While the demonstrated switching is centered around 1000 nm, the operational wavelength can be tailored during fabrication by tuning the nanocrystal size. Smaller or larger VO₂ nanocrystals are expected to induce a blue- or redshift, respectively, in the resonant absorption due to size-dependent modifications of the localized surface plasmon resonances.

In conclusion, we have demonstrated that ultrafast photoexcitation of a VO₂ nanocrystal-based metamaterial enables fluence-controlled, linear graded modulation of optical absorption via the photoinduced insulator-to-metal transition. Unlike VO₂ thin films, where the optical response is spectrally broad and featureless, the nanocrystal geometry confines the switching functionality to a well-defined LSPR near 1000 nm. The transient response displays a strictly

linear fluence dependence, providing deterministic access to a continuous set of intermediate absorption states, and the platform sustains at least 10^7 consecutive switching cycles without measurable degradation. The demonstrated analog tunability and confirmed cyclability further suggest the potential of this platform for neuromorphic photonic applications.

See the [supplementary material](#) for the comparison between bulk VO₂ and the nanocrystal metamaterial optical response, together with the complete transient dielectric function dynamics and fitting parameters.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Yael Gutierrez: Conceptualization (lead); Data curation (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Funding acquisition (lead); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (lead); Software (lead); Supervision (lead); Validation (lead); Visualization (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Saul Vazquez-Miranda:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Mateusz Rebarz:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Shirly Espinoza:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Helmut Karl:** Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Jose M. Saiz:** Investigation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Sébastien Cuffé:** Conceptualization (lead); Investigation (equal); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://zenodo.org/records/15348298> (Ref. 30).

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